

Dioramas of the natural world: Brazilian primary school pupils' drawings

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Resumo

Visitantes vão a um museu para observar dioramas de história natural, com uma riqueza prévia de conhecimentos relevantes e experiências bem com expectativas, as quais podem ter diferenças entre os componentes do mesmo grupo visitante. O museu que alberga os dioramas também tem sua própria "voz" que se faz ouvir no contexto no qual os dioramas estão situados e no formato que os dioramas estes assumem, bem como a interpretação fornecida pelo contexto, a história dos dioramas na perspectiva ecológica e geográfica. Este estudo exploratório considera qual possa ser o impacto que os dioramas da vida selvagem terão no conteúdo dos desenhos executados por 28 meninas e 31 meninos, alunos de escola particular. Salienta-se que a compreensão que as crianças terão dos organismos, foi investigado pelo modelo mental revelado por meio de seus desenhos (modelo expresso). Levou-se em consideração que o desenho pré-visita foi o que os alunos anteciparam que veriam no museu, e o pós-visita o que lembram que viram neste local. O modelo mental é o conhecimento científico (aspecto animal e habitat ecológico). As crianças dessa investigação revelaram nas suas representações pós-visita, maior conhecimento principalmente de mamíferos e pássaros, mas um mínimo de relações ecológicas e plantas.

Palavras chave: Dioramas, Desenhos, Crianças, Modelo Mental, Taxidermia.

Abstract

People come to the museum to look at natural history dioramas with a wealth of previous relevant knowledge and experience as well as expectations, which may differ amongst members of the same visiting group. The museum which houses the dioramas also has its own "voice" heard through in the context in which the dioramas are sited and in the form that the dioramas take as well as interpretations provided about the content, the story of

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the dioramas from the perspective ecological and geographic. This exploratory study considers which impact wildlife dioramas may have on the content of drawings performed by twenty-eight girls and thirty-one boys enrolled in a private school. Children's understanding about organisms may be investigated by examining the mental model revealed through their drawings, their expressed model, of what they anticipate they will see and what they recall they have seen after such a visit. The mental model is the scientific knowledge (appearance of the animal and its ecological habitat). Children from this investigation revealed in their post-visit representations a larger knowledge mainly of mammals and birds but almost nothing about ecological relationships and plants.

Keywords: Dioramas, Drawing, Children, Mental Model, Taxidermy.

1. Introduction

A diorama is a careful positioning of a number of museum objects in a naturalistic setting and typically combines preserved organisms and painted or modeled landscape (Borg, 2009; Reiss & Tunnicliffe, 2011) [1, 2]. Natural history dioramas have four characteristics of design. Firstly, the correct species of animals and plants are shown together, this is in geographical terms as well as natural relationships, particularly feeding (Scott, 2005) [3]. Secondly, animals are usually depicted doing something interesting. Thirdly, dioramas of museum animals have a distinctive calm and stillness about them. They offer occasional visitors opportunity to stand and stare as benches are provided and also stimulate story telling (Tomkins and Tunnicliffe, 2001; Reiss et al., 2007) [4, 5]. This is good for autistic children and adults (Coplan, 2010; Grandin and Panek, 2013; Borges et al., 2018) [6-8]. Fourthly even though they may depict acts of predation, natural history dioramas often have a "heaven" feel to them. There is no representation of disease or malnutrition-animals are shown in the prime of their health and physical fitness.

This, "ideal world" has been noted elsewhere in children's drawings (Reiss et al. 2007). [5] They reflect an idealistic view of reality, a view of "what should be" rather than "what really is" (Tunnicliffe, 2015). [9]

When visitors look at biological exhibits they may construct meaning from what they watch with more care either animals, vegetable or minerals or constructed artifacts and verbalize items recognized as rocks animal names or plants providing a context provided by the diorama. Natural History dioramas are a historical repository mainly of animals, plants

and environments components as weather and minerals. However, they in fact may be regarded although old and out of date as an essential and optimum tool to assist learners in constructing understanding the basic ideas of biodiversity and past climate (Scheersoi et al., 2009) [10]. As such as exhibits in a museum they communicate messages from a variety of underpinning areas, biological, ecological, environmental, historical through the medium of the exhibit, the diorama. They are a record of past biodiversity and habitats, which compared with today, reflect changes due to both climate and human activity (Tunnicliffe, 2002; Marandino et al., 2009) [11, 12]. The animals exposed in a museum, particularly of Natural History do not agree according to the museum theory a gender of cultural artifacts because they occur in nature and are not man-made (Henning, 2006). [13] The museum animals obviously are "not alive" as their inner structures are replaced by the taxidermist in the construction of the exhibit following traditional taxidermy (Huorta, 1986). [14] However, the image of the animal is preserved as it was alive and provides the visitor with a valuable opportunity to look at the exemplar with fidelity and meaning. This permit posture is a characteristic of showing a typical behavior which occasionally contributes for a profitable dialog and understanding than when observing alive exemplars in other environments (Patrick and Tunnicliffe, 2012) [15].

In Natural History museums where taxidermitized animals are exhibited in 3 dimensions, are the essence of natural world dioramas it created. The animals belonging to the natural world, differently from those exhibited in a science institution;

emphasize a story as they are immersed in a context where they lived together with ecological, meteorological and geological phenomena (Scheersoi and Tunnicliffe, 2010). [16] Besides, the overlap of knowledge such as topics allows possibilities for studies of viable interactions or a picture of scenes depicting predator and prey as in the real world (Peart and Kool, 1988). [17] Dioramas reflect or contribute to construct reality. Visitors come to the diorama on their visits with some previous knowledge to what they are going to see. Other identified message is what visitors bring in their interpretation of the museum message.

Brazil and the small island of Malta have lots of common features related to education. Rote learning is highly predominant in the classrooms, pupils active learning is not sufficiently encouraged and outdoors learning experiences are very limited (Knight, 2009) [18]. The authors choose to research these museum settings mainly because they are predominantly naturalistic exhibits that focus on Biology and the environment. This kind of research have important implications on early Biological and Environmental educational in Brazil, and the way of learning about animals and plants is affected in primary schools. Children either in Brazil or Malta have limited opportunities for direct contact with the fauna and flora in the wild. It is well known that many children depend on their parents' interest to be able to experience the diversity in fauna and flora typical of Brazilian habitats (Mifsud, 2015a-b) [19, 20]. Increasing urbanization and declining populations of various species have reduced opportunities for children to directly experience organisms in the wild (Huxham et al., 2006) [21]. The habitat dioramas showing conceptual dioramas of local natural history habitats at "The Museum of Natural History of Capão da Imbuia" are an underutilized educational resource. Dioramas may serve as an early stimulus for children to recognize and become further familiar with their local biodiversity. Habitat dioramas are a valuable resource for museum education (Marnadinia & Oliveira, 2009) [22]. Dioramas have been a rather neglected area by educationalists but changes are underway to highlight their educational importance in contributing to children understanding of the natural world (Tunnicliffe, 2005) [23-25].

1.1 Curitiba and Sea Mountain Range fauna.

The following amphibians and reptiles are found in local backyards and Marumby peak area 50 km from downtown: toads (*Rhinella ictericia*), (*Brachycephalus ferruginus*), (*Proceratophrys distincta*) and tree-frogs (*Hypsiboas faber*), (*Phyllomedusa distincta*). Snakes such as (*Bothrops jararaca*), the coral snake (*Micrurus altirostris*), the green snake (*Philodryas olfersii*) and a kind of fresh water turtles (*Hydromedusa tectifera*) the later mostly found at the Marumby area. Opussums are also commonly found as for example *Didelphis aurita*, *Didelphis albiventris*. Other xenartra are seen as the smaller anteater (*Tamandua tetradactyla*), the armadillo (*Dasyopsus novemcintus*). A few primates as the "nail-monkey" (*Cebus apela*) and "red bugio" (*Alouatta guariba*) and small carnivorous animals as for example the forest dog (*Cerdocyon thous*), the racoon (*Nasua nasua*), (*Procyon cancrivorus*) tayra (*Eira barbara*) and the ferret (*Galictis cuja*) and the jaguar (*Puma concolor*), (*Panthera onca*) dwarf leopardo [Brazilian wild cat] (*Leopardus pardalis*) as well as other wild cats such as *Leopardus tigrinus*, *L. Wiedii*, and *Puma yagouaroundi* are found close to the Marumby peak, (Alves,2008) [26].

Other animals include the deer (*Mazama gouazoubira*), the pecary (*Pecari tajacu*) and representatives of rodentia as the agouti (*Dasyprocta azarae*), Paca? (*Agouti paca*), Brazilian squirrel (*Sciurus ingrami*), guinea pig (*Cavia aperea*) and the only Brazilian rabbit, cottontail rabbit (*Sylvilagus brasiliensis*), (Alves,2008) [26].

There a large number of birds in the Marumbi area which fly to Curitiba. Among those the most popular are: the Golden-sided euphonia (*Euphoria violacea*), the solitary tinamou (*Tinamus solitarius*), woodpeckers (*Celeus flavescens*, *Picumnus temminckii*), the guan (*Pipile jacutinga*), toucan (*Ramphastos vitellinus*), blue jay (*Cyanocorax caeruleus*), the bellbird (*Procnias nudicollis*), the hawk (*Spizaetus tyrannus*) the crown (*Coragyps atratus*) and the kingfisher (*Chloroceryle amazona*). Most of these species are represented as objects into the dioramas at the Museum of Natural History of the Capão da Imbuia, Curitiba (Alves, 2008; Zamoner et al., 2012). [26, 27]

Dioramas have been a rather neglected area by educationalists but changes are underway to highlight their educational importance in contributing to children understanding of the natural world (Tunncliffe, 2005) [23-25].

1.2 Biological topic

This study evaluates in an accurate environment the visual impact which dioramas composed by wild animals and plants play on the contents of drawings made by pupils from a public school before and after a visit to the dioramas at the Natural History Museum of “Capão da Embuia”, Curitiba, Paraná State-Brazil.

Pupil’s understanding about organisms may be investigated by examining the mental models (personal knowledge of the phenomena) revealed through their drawings, i. e. the expressed model, of what they anticipate they will see and what they remember they have seen after the visit to the dioramas (Bjork, 2000). [28]

This kind of scientific knowledge may present similarities and disagreements to current contemporaneous scientific knowledge, as for instance the characteristics of the animals and plants related to their ecological habitat (Reiss and Tunncliffe, 1999). [29]

What impacts pupils from preschool and primary school more are the gross anatomical features when they observe the display of organisms in the windows? These features may be revealed by graphical representations from authentic specimens which are mentally constructed by the step by step integration between the real object, the mental model and the drawing, i. e. the expressed model (Tunncliffe, 1997) [31]. What children and adults see in their minds is their mental model. What they saw, or draw about the exhibit is their expressed model, which draws on information held within their mental model (Buckley, et al., 1997). [32]

2. Theoretical framework

Previous studies have shown that comments made at zoos on live animals did not vary so much from those at museums preserved animals and plants (Tunncliffe, 1996). [33]

When observing museum animals on visits, pupils refer mainly to anatomical features rather than behavioral or habitat related cues (Reiss and Tunncliffe, 1999) [29]. Due to increasing urbanization town in developing countries are missing the “green belt” around them and thus are reducing opportunities children progressively are lacking experience with wildlife (except in zoos) but do know about them. It is claimed by some that an urbanized generation will have a scarce knowledge and interest in wildlife (Huxham et al., 2006; Zamoner et al., 2012; Louv, 2008). [21, 27, 30] However, children are in touch with wildlife in their environment in the early years (Bartoszeck and Tunncliffe, 2013; Rybska and Tunncliffe, 2014; Rybska et al., 2015). [34-36] But, dioramas are valuable depository to the urban community for understanding the different habitats or exotic endemic species in this environ and interactions between organisms usually seem in a few textbooks and media. They turn to be a powerful tool in biological education (Tunncliffe, 2005) [23-25]. Very few empirical studies have made use and evaluated the potential of drawings in elucidating scientific understanding. For example, Mifsud (2015) [19, 20]. compares drawings executed by children before a visit to a Natural History Museum in Malta with dioramas to determine prior knowledge and expectations and then afterwards to find out what they remember and how they interpret the interrelationship between animals plants and environment exposed in the dioramas they saw. Mifsud proposed an “interpretation model” which is based on Activity System (Mifsud, 2015a-b Engstrom et al., 1999) [19, 20, 37].

Using drawings to collect data have many advantages over other means. The technique allows obtaining a large mass of data in an easy and inexpensive way related to pupil’s mental models from the natural world, avoiding the problem of language issues specially with young children (Reiss et al., 2002) [38]. Drawings may be a rich source of evidence how children think in most curricular areas (Gardner, 2011; Nutbrown, 2011) [39, 40]. Thus, dioramas communicate messages from a variety of related areas such as biological, ecological, environmental historical through the medium of the exhibition, the dioramas. As a record of past biodiversity and

habitats, which compared with today, reflect changes due to both climate and human activity but, also showing a world free of disease and injury. Visitors and school children following their school curriculum are able to recognize, identify and interpret interconnections between predators and prey as well as other phenomena such as flora and fauna of biomes, climatic features, whose interactions zoos are largely unable to show. As dioramas are presented as science exhibits to arrest the attention of visitors may lead to develop further reading and learning. Children who have difficulty with verbal expression may through drawings show things they cannot put into words (Bowker, 2007) [41].

3. Aims and research questions

- What is the understanding pupils 6 years old to 12 years old have of organisms through the observation of eight wildlife dioramas and five biomes at the Museum of Natural History of Capão da Imbuia, Curitiba, Paraná State, Brazil?
- What is the value of children's drawings as representing of understanding of animals and plants have?
- It intends to find out clues from this understanding comparing pre- and post-visit drawings of the exhibits in the dioramas.

4. Methodology

Drawings is a non-threatening tool which can provide a non-verbal means of communication and has the potential to allow children to express their experiences, feelings and opinions (Brooks, 2005). [42] Still, to use them to diagnose children's knowledge is useful to make explicit their beliefs and attitudes to everyday life (Moussouri, 1997) [43].

The researchers contacted two public primary schools that had agreed to allow their pupils to participate in this study. The head teachers of the school concerned dealt with the ethical issues of parental consent and procedures. The fieldwork was carried out in the Southern part of Brazil in Curitiba, State of Paraná. The suburban school is a private institution. The second researcher visit the class two

days before the museum visit, and after the pupils (N = 32) had been told about the dioramas they expected to see, asked to draw on a blank A4 sheet of paper which animals and plants they might see at the Museum of Natural History of Capão da Imbuia.

The drawings were executed in a larger classroom than the pupil's normal one, where each second desk was left unoccupied in order to avoid, as far as possible, children copying from each other and from textbooks. Children were asked to draw in silence and asked to write their first names and ages at the top of the page.

The drawings were collected during a regular period of the class and children were given about 15 minutes to finish the task.

4.1 Dioramas at the Natural History Museum of Capão da Imbuia (Curitiba, Paraná)

The first diorama depicts a Brazilian savana (cerrado in Portuguese) with the following animals in the window exhibit: a maned Wolf (Lobo-guará), *Chrysocyon brachyurus*, a six-banded armadillo (Tatu-peba), *Euphractus sexcintus*, a rattlesnake (Cascavel), *Crotalus durissus* a Blue tegu (Teiú) *Tupinambis meriang*. Birds representing the Brazilian savana were: a greater rhea (Ema, *Rhea americana*), a king vulture (Urubú-rei, *Sarcoramphus papa*), a buff-necked ibis (Curicaca, *Theristicus caudatus*), a hyacinth macaw (Arara-azul-grande, *Anodorhynchus hyacinthinus*), a yellow-faced parrot (Papagaio galego, *Amazona xanthops*), a white-tailed hawk (Gavião-de-rabo-branco, *Geranoetus albicaetus*), a campo flicker (Pica-pau do campo, *Colaptes campestris*).

The second diorama depicts a Brazilian tropical forest (Floresta tropical) with the following animals in the exhibit: a Jaguar (Onça-pintada, *Panthera onca*), a Tapir (Anta, *Tapirus terrestris*), a Paca (Paca, *Agouti paca*), a Little-red brochet (Veado-bororó, *Mazana rufina*), a Blue-winged parrotlet (Tuim, *Forpus xan*), a Rufous-capped marmot (Juruva, *Baryphthegus ruficapilus*), a Saffron toucanet (Araçari-banana, *Pteroraglossus bailami*).

The third diorama depicts an Araucaria forest (floresta com araucárias) with pine trees in the background of the panel and the following animals in the exhibit: an Agouti (*Cutia, Dasyprocta azarae*),

an Ocelot (Jaguatitica, *Leopardus pardalis*), a Tayra (Irara, *Eira barbara*), a Brazilian squirrel (Serelepe, *Guelinguetus ingrami*), an Orange-spined hairy dwarf porcupine (Ouriço-chaceiro, *Sphigurus vilisous*), a Red-breasted toucan (Tucano-de-bico-verde, *Ramphastos dicolorous*), a white-tailed hawk (Gavião quiri-quiri, *Falco sparverius*), a giant antshrike (Matracão, *Batara cinerea*), a plush-crested jay (Gralha-picaça, *Cyanocorax chrysops*), a lined woodpecker (Pica-pau-de banda branca, *Dryocopus lineatus*), a blue jay (Gralha azul, *Cyanocorax caeruleus*) a blue-fronted parrot (Papagaio, *Amazona aestiva*), a Vinaceous-breasted parrot (Papagaio-peito-roxo, *Amazona vinacea*).

The fourth diorama depicts an Aquatic environment (Ambiente aquático) with the following animals in the exhibit: a nutria (Ratão-do-banhado, *Myacastor coypus*), an American anhinga (Biguatinga, *Anhinga anhinga*), a green kingfisher (Martin-pescador, *Chloroceryle americana*), a white-faced whistling-duck (Marreca-irerê, *Dendrocygna viduata*), a muscovy duck (Pato-do-mato, *Cairina moschata*), a black-crowned heron (Socó-dorminhoco, *Nycticorax nycticorax*), a fulvous whistling-duck (Marreca-caneleira, *Dendrocygna bicolor*), a common moorhen (Frango-d'água, *Gallinula chloropus*).

The fifth diorama depicts an urban environment (Ambiente urbano) with a little hut and a background panel with an araucaria arboretum and other vegetation and high skyscrapers in the distance. The following animals are exhibited: an opossum (Gambá, *Didelphis albiventris*), a toad (Sapo-cururu, *Rhinedia ictérica*), a butter frog (Rã-manteiga *Leptodactylus fatrans*), a house-mouse (Camundongo, *Mus musculus*), a brown rat (Ratazana, *Rattus norvegicus*), a rock dove (Pombadoméstica, *Columba livia*).

The sixth diorama exhibits a group of threatened species having at the background some local trees, shrubs and other vegetation. The following animals are exhibited: Giant anteater (tamanduá-bandeira, *Myrmecophaga tridactyla*), a vinegar dog (chachorro-vinagre, *Speothus venaticus*), a little spotted cat (Gato-do-mato, *Leopardus tigrinus*), a brown howling monkey (Bugio, *Alouatta guariba*), a black-fronted piping-guan (Jacutinga, *Pipile*

jacutinga), a red-and green macaw (Arara-vermelha, *Ara chloropterus*).

The seventh diorama depicts an environment with sparse vegetation where raptors live and the following animals are depicted: an owl, a crow, a rook, and a hawk. The eighth and last diorama depicts a marine environment with a skeleton of a large whale, a turtle, a penguin, a sea-gull other water front birds. Note: all dioramas were visited by the first author before pupils came for the task.

On the Natural History Museum visit the pupils observed dioramas in groups of 3 or 4 pupils and the researcher was with each group. Back to school after the visit the researcher asked the groups to draw what they had seen in the dioramas. The pre- and post-visit drawings were analysed on the basis of biological detail and ecological relationships, if any (Tunncliffe, 2002). [11]

5. Results

5.1 Analysis of the drawings

The purpose of classroom drawings was to gauge the children's present familiarity with local fauna and flora before visiting the museum. It was also to determine whether the novelty of the museum visit would produce any significant effect on the children's drawing compared to that produced in classroom. The analysis of the drawings generated the following categories: animal, plant, context, graphic, physical, Table (1).

Table 1. Class task categories defined.

Animal	Any graphical item recognized as an animal, for example squirrel.
Plant	Any graphical item recognized as a plant, for example a pine tree.
Context	Drawing showing organisms in context, for example a farm, garden.
Graphic	A property of graphical nature: color, black and white, anthropomorphic feature.
Physical	Any abiotic feature in the drawing, for example: sun, soil.

Table 2. Class task category drawings.

Category	Pupils drawing feature	%
Animal	101	100.00
Plant	0	0.00
Context	2	0.72
Color	0	0.00
Black & white	101	100.00
Anthropomorphic	14	5.04
Physical	0	0.00

Numbers of drawings in each category: 36.

Table 3. Class task animal subordinate group (taxon) drawings.

Taxonomic group	No. Drawings	Drawings (%)
Amphibian	1	0.9
Arthropod	9	8.9
Bird	16	15.8
Cnidarian	3	2.9
Crustacean	1	0.9
Echinoderm	2	1.9
Fish	11	10.8
Mammal	35	34.6
Mollusk	6	5.9
Reptile	12	11.8
Chelonia	3	2.9
Nemathelminthes	1	0.9
Oligochaeta	2	1.9

The majority of the pre-visit drawings collected from the children showed an animal outlines familiar to pupils from home or urban and suburban environments and other sources (e. g. Zoos, other

kind of museums) and a lack of plant life. Most contained less than two animals and a few had more than nine.

The Table (2) shows that the animal category scored the highest followed by plants with appreciably lower numbers. Almost all drawings show at least a single animal but no plants. Animal average by drawing was (2.8) compared with that for plants (0.0), bearing evidence to a greater preference for drawings animals rather than plants. In the graphic category all drawings (100%) were in black and white and no drawing show labeled organism. A proportion (5.04%) of the drawings (14), show anthropomorphism. No abiotic feature was represented on the drawings.

Table 4. Type of organism drawn in the respective taxonomic group.

Taxonomic group	Organism drawn
Amphibian	Toad, frog.
Bird	Goose, sparrow, owl, toucan, parrot, duck, hen, canary, penguin, ostrich, cockatiel.
Cnidarian/ Coelenterate	Portuguese man of war, jellyfish.
Crustacean	Crab, sand-crab, shrimp.
Fish	Shark, trout, sea-horse, puffer, stingray, carp, sardine, trout, sea-horse.
Arthropod	Spider, centipede, millipede, fly, ant.
Mammal	Cat, rabbit, sheep, horse, dog, hamster, monkey, camel, jaguar, giraffe, tiger, lion, whale, elephant.
Mollusk	Snail, octopus.
Reptile	Lizard, snake, alligator, coral-snake, crocodile.
Echinoderm	Starfish.
Nemathelminthes	Leech.
Oligochaeta	Earthworm.
Chelonia	Turtle.

The number in the animal category was further subdivided into the subordinate taxonomic groups: amphibian, arthropod, bird, cnidarian, crustacean, fish, echinoderm, mammal, mollusk reptile, Platyhelminthes and oligochaeta. The animal category had the largest number (34.6%) meaning it showed the highest variety of organisms. The second largest number of the animals drawn were birds (15.8%) followed by reptile (11.8%), fish (10.8%) and arthropods (8.9%). It was interesting to note a variety of species represented in the drawings.

Table 5. Total number of animals represented on the drawings before and after visiting the Natural History Museum (dioramas).

Animal	Before visit	After visit
Bird	17	35
Fish	8	10
Little spotted cat	6	13
Vinegar dog	8	14
Rabbit	2	5
Monkey	3	6
Jaguar	2	1
Black rat	2	3
Snake	7	16
Turtle	6	10
Penguin	0	10
Whale	0	10
Owl	0	10
Butterfly	1	6
Crab	2	4

The organism drawn and the respective taxonomic group are shown in Table 4. A total 57 drawings represented different animals. The largest taxonomic group was mammals (24.5%) followed by birds (19.3%) fishes (12.3%), and reptiles (10.5%). The

least represented were the earthworm and leech (5.3%).

The majority of the pre-visit drawings collected from the children showed animal outlines familiar to pupils from home or urban and suburban environments and other sources (e. g. Zoos, other kind of museums) and a lack of plant life. Most contained less than two animals and a few had more than nine, Table (5).

The main identifiable vertebrate animals represented in the drawings with 1 to 3 mentions in the pre-visit included: horse, camel, sheep, alligator, lion, tiger, elephant, giant anteater, hippopotamus, bear, pig, giraffe, armadillo, toad, lizard, agouti. And the main invertebrates represented included: scorpion, snail, earthworm, spider, starfish, Portuguese man of war, bee, ant, butterfly, crab, seahorse, stingray, shrimp, octopus, praying mantis.

Some of the pupils wrote the name of the animals near the drawing. No ecological relationships were evident in any of the pre-visit drawings.

The post-visit drawings indicated that the natural history dioramas experience influenced pupils' ability to draw a larger representation of animals. For instance the category bird included: hen, owl, duck, goose and rhea. All drawings were done using a black pencil and no color was used. However, no trees or flowers were included in the drawings as well as ecological relationships shown.

All animals were drawn in two dimensions with horizontal body displayed in side view as represented by the pre-diorama drawing depicting a monkey, Figure (1).

The parrot is disproportionate in relation to the rest of the items in the picture (diorama drawing, post visit) while the Octopus is only partially represented with smaller tentacles, Figure (2).

The desire to create a likeness to the real object is evident in the alligator (pre-diorama visit) depicting only two animals, Figure (3), but plenty of them although in smaller sizes to fit in the sheet of paper, Figure (4).

Figure 1. Drawing by a boy 12 years old before visiting the Museum of Natural History of Capão da Imbuia.

6. Discussion

This investigation involved a group of 12 years old boys and girls attending a private primary school in southern Brazil. It was partly conducted in the classroom where the children drew animals and plants they anticipated would see at the Museum of Natural History of Capão da Imbuia. Drawings done in the classroom were regarded as an expression of the children mental model of indigenous animals and plants countrywide. The children were at the museum to experience and learn about specimens held there, but particularly to observe the local habitat dioramas. This study is an attempt to conceptualize habitat dioramas as a potential model for biological learning of local fauna and flora. Previous research has not considered how dioramas can enable the visualization of animals and plants with educational value. Although the potential dioramas have to be a valuable tool in biological learning they are not featured in any major museum publication (Hein, 1998; 1999; Falk & Dierking, 2000; Paris, 2002; Black, 2005) [42-46]. A constructivist perspective is taken since it views learning as the building of mental models. Drawings in this investigation showed that mental models of different children are

expressed in personal and distinct forms different from their classmates.

During the post-visit drawings a larger number of animals were represented. The results indicated that watching the dioramas enabled pupils to observe with meaning which was manifested in drawings after the visit to the museum. This may provide a starting point for educators accompanying school groups, for developing specific classroom activities addressing the role animals' play into ecological relationships [47-51].

Figure 2. Drawing by the same boy after visiting the Museum of Natural History of Capão da Imbuia.

Figure 3. Drawing by a girl 12 years old before visiting the Museum of Natural History of Capão da Imbuia.

7. Conclusion

This study is based on a relatively small number of pupils enrolled in a private primary school with a fifty-nine participating pupils and it is not therefore representative of other areas from either Paraná State or Brazil. Five pupils who participated in the classroom drawing task did not attend the museum visit, thus reducing the sample size further. A limitation for this investigation is the small sample and lack of a range of ages to allow comparisons. Further investigation will be carried in the near future.

School authorities can also encourage schools to undertake visits to natural history museums and science centers, especially those that do not charge fees, as this could increase children's biological understanding. Probing children's thinking about fauna and flora can be a starting point for more effective teaching in the classroom. This requires that science teachers are able to elicit children's existing biological knowledge, and to promote ways to enable the construction of new knowledge.

Figure 4. Drawing by the same girl after visiting the Museum of Natural History of Capão da Imbuia.

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